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Effect of Al₂O₃ addition on the properties of Lead Titanate Glass-ceramics

Abstract: - Glasses with different weight proportions of Al₂O₃ have been synthesized by melt-quench method. Prepared glasses were given two stage heat treatment to convert them into glass-ceramics. In these glass-ceramic samples it is observed that the density, room temperature dielectric constant and percentage of lead titanate phase increased with Al₂O₃ addition. These glass-ceramic samples have shown ferroelectric property and it has been observed that the value of remnant polarization increased with Al₂O₃ addition. The enhancement in the values of remnant polarization was due to increase in the volume fraction of PbTiO₃ phase as measured from XRD.

Keywords: Glass-ceramics, XRD, PbTiO₃, Dielectric constant, Ferroelectric properties.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In 1950, Lead titanate was reported to be ferroelectric on the basis of its structural properties compared with BaTiO₃. The high transition temperature around 490 °C [1] exhibited by PbTiO₃ make this material useful for high temperature applications. Controlled crystallization of glasses led to a development of polycrystalline solids known as glass-ceramics [2]. These materials can be used as an insulator for high voltages, substrates for electronic circuits, dielectric and piezoelectric devices [2-3]. Lead titanate (PbTiO₃) is a typical ferroelectric material having perovskite structure with $T_c \sim 490$ °C. It is difficult to prepare the undoped lead titanate ceramic material due to large anisotropy. The glass-ceramic route, therefore, offers the possibility of fabricating lead titanate without cracking [4]. The lead titanate based glass-ceramic have been studied widely. However very few reports are available on the effect of Al₂O₃ addition on structural, dielectric and ferroelectric properties of lead titanate containing glass-ceramic.

In this work systematic addition of Al₂O₃ at the cost of B₂O₃ was done to enhance the dielectric and ferroelectric properties of these glass-ceramics.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

The glasses with composition 60PbO : 25TiO₂ : (15-X)B₂O₃ : XAl₂O₃ (with X= 0, 2.5, 5, 7.5 and 10 mol%) were prepared from highly pure chemicals. The mix dry powders with different weight proportions were transferred to 5 different 50 ml alumina crucibles, which then heated up to 1250-1300 °C. The melt was soaked for 1 h and homogenized by stirring it before quenching into the copper mould at room temperature. The resultant glass samples were annealed at 400 °C for three hours to remove the residual stresses. The glass transition temperature T_g and crystallization temperature T_c for the glass were determined from DTA. The glass samples were converted to glass-ceramics by following the two stage heat treatment. The glass samples were nucleated for 16 h and crystallized for 16 h, at 425 °C and 480 °C respectively. The density of these glass-ceramics was measured by Archimedes principle with toluene as an emersion liquid.

The XRD patterns of glass-ceramics were recorded with Xpert PANalytical diffractometer. In glass-ceramic samples it was desired to have maximum percentage of formation of perovskite PbTiO₃ phase. Therefore its (PbTiO₃) volume fraction was calculated from XRD. The room temperature dielectric constant of glass-ceramic samples was measured using high resolution dielectric alpha analyzer. The ferroelectric hysteresis measurements were performed using automatic PE loop tracer.

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III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Density of the glass-ceramic samples has been observed to increase with Al₂O₃ addition. The maximum density 6.55 gm/cm³ was obtained for 10 mol % Al₂O₃ containing glass-ceramic sample. The increase in density with Al₂O₃ addition may be due to higher mass of Aluminum compared to that of Boron which increases the rigidity of glass-ceramic samples.

The XRD patterns of the glass-ceramic samples have been depicted in figure 1. XRD results shows that lead titanate is the major crystalline phase in the glass-ceramic samples. All the major peaks matched very well with the tetragonal lead titanate phase (JCPDS file no-78-0298). The volume fraction of lead titanate phase was calculated by comparing the integral intensities of amorphous, glass-ceramic and completely crystalline samples from X-ray diffraction patterns [5]. The volume fraction of PbTiO₃ phase is (shown in table 1) observed to increase with Al₂O₃ addition. The replacement of B₂O₃ by Al₂O₃ led to enhance the perovskite PbTiO₃ content in glass-ceramics as confirmed from XRD.

Fig 1. XRD Patterns for Glass-ceramic samples.

The room temperature dielectric constant of the glass-ceramic samples has been measured at 1 kHz which shows increasing trend with the Al_2O_3 addition (Table 1). The values of dielectric constant obtained in the present work are higher than those reported in the literature for PbTiO_3 containing glass-ceramics [6, 7]. The increase in dielectric constant may be correlated to the increased volume fraction of formation of tetragonal PbTiO_3 phase in glass-ceramic samples.

The ferroelectric hysteresis measurements were carried out at room temperature. The samples were poled at 5 kV for 30 minutes. The values of remnant polarization is given in table 1. From the table 1 it is observed that there is an increase in the values of remnant polarization with Al_2O_3 addition.

Fig 2. Representative PE Hysteresis Loop for 7.5 Al_2O_3 containing Glass-ceramic sample.

The observed increase in remnant polarization for glass-ceramic samples may be attributed to the formation of tetragonal lead titanate phase whose content was observed to increase with Al_2O_3 addition. Fig.2 shows the ferroelectric hysteresis loop for the 7.5 mol % Al_2O_3 containing glass-ceramic sample. The non-saturated loops were observed in all the samples which could be due to the presence of residual glass phase and the stress applied by the rigid glass matrix [8, 9]. The ceramic-glass interface plays an important role in causing the non-saturated hysteresis loops. This phenomenon is believed to be due to interfacial polarization [10, 11].

These are preliminary results, and further enhancement in P_r can be obtained by optimizing the processing parameters of the glass-ceramics.

TABLE 1. Values of Room Temperature Dielectric Constant, Volume Fraction of PbTiO₃, Remnant Polarization and Coercive Field for Glass-ceramic Samples.

Mol % Al ₂ O ₃	Dielectric Constant at 1 kHz	Volume Fraction of PbTiO ₃ (%)	P _r (μC/cm ²)
0	113	54.19	0.010
2.5	117	55.02	0.015
5	120	57.68	0.018
7.5	129	58.11	0.038
10	134	58.69	0.049

IV CONCLUSION

The density, dielectric constant and volume fraction lead titanate increases with Al₂O₃ addition. The presence of ferroelectricity in these glass-ceramic samples makes them useful for transducers applications for which further investigation is needed.

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